

ICCM24

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High Resolution Induction Sensing for Feature Detection in Thin-ply Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer

Ehshan ul-Haq
Baris Caglar
Clemens Dransfeld

Thin-ply CFRP

- Thin-ply CFRP has typical thickness of around 100µm or less
- Intermediate product
- Thin-ply tapes have several benefits over conventional CFRP tapes
 - Strength
 - Damage tolerance
 - Design flexibility
- High performance applications
- Homogeneous manufacturing is not trivial

Section of Unidirectional CFRP tape. Arkema.

Ultimate strength and onset of damage with respect to ply thickness in unnotched quasi-isotropic laminate. Amacher, 2014.

Thin-ply CFRP

- Example application of material flexibility

a. Rolled up

b. In deployment

Manufacturing at Delft TapeLab

Manufacturing at Delft TapeLab

Tension-controlled reels

Processing line

UDCFRP tape

Difficulties and defects

CFRP tape with various defects

Cross-sectional micrograph of UDCFRP tape – notable defects

Cross-sectional micrograph of UDCFRP tape – lesser defects

Difficulties and defects

Ideal material

Tightly stacked fibers with high fiber-volume fraction

Real-life material

Randomly stacked with heterogeneous fiber-volume fraction

Virtual twin

Monitoring and NDT

Adjust processing settings to optimize material

Or accept material as is and compensate in tape laying operation

Automated fiber placement. DLR.

Tape manufacturing

Monitoring and NDT

Multiple techniques exist to assess the microstructure

- Optical analysis
- X-Ray analysis
- Electromagnetic analysis
- And more...

- + Cheap
- + Fast
- Limited to surface assessment

Photo image of CFRP tow in spreading process. Ul-Haq, 2023.

- + Extremely high resolution
- Small scan volume
- Expensive
- Potentially dangerous

X-Ray scan of CFRP tape. Gomarasca, 2021.

Monitoring and NDT

Multiple techniques exist to assess the microstructure

- Optical analysis
- X-Ray analysis
- **Electromagnetic analysis**
- And more...

- + Through-thickness measurement
- + Potential for fast acquisition time
- Sensitive to noise

Current-flow depends on conductor properties such as:

- Conductivity,
- Thickness,
- Homogeneity, ..

Principle of Eddy-Current sensing

Methodology

Drive coil with generated function

Purposely defected UD CFRP Tape

Returned signal can be expressed as complex with a **Phase-Shift ϕ** and **Impedance Z** component

Input Voltage

Output Voltage

Methodology

Purposely defected UD CFRP Tape

X position

Sensor is moved across the tape

Fiber content varies over tape width

Example fibrous content

X position

$\Delta\phi$

Input Voltage

Output Voltage

Measurement is made at every coordinate

Methodology

Results

Areal scan of defected CFRP tape

W = H = 20mm

CFRP tape with intentionally induced excessive defects (T700SC50 + PEEK)

Fibrous volume vs. Normalized phase-shift intensity

- Correlation in fiber-volume and sensor response

Results

Areal scan of defected CFRP tape

W = H = 20mm

Defected CFRP tape with resin-rich streak (T700SC50 + PEEK)

Averaged signal vs. fiber content per width of defected CFRP tape for 39 MHz

Cross-sectional micrograph of defected CFRP tape

Results

Areal scan of defected CFRP tape

W = H = 20mm

Defected CFRP tape with fuzz/waviness (T700SC50 + PEEK)

Averaged signal vs. fiber content per width of defected CFRP tape for 39 MHz

Cross-sectional micrograph of defected CFRP tape

Conclusions, limitations, and recommendations

- Able to detect fiber-rich / resin-rich streaks in UD CFRP tape

- Able to detect fuzzy or wavy regions in UD CFRP tape

- Not able to detect fibrous content in the sub-mm range in UD CFRP tape; lacks ability to distinguish large volumes far away or small volumes close-by

Future work:

- Improved assembly for increased accuracy
- Investigation into industrial implementation
- Further studies into repeatability
- Assessment of responses for various fiber-matrix combinations

Thank you!

Please visit the QR code for further information about the TU Delft TapeLab:

Rijksdienst voor Ondernemend
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